

THE NATIONAL HANDICRAFTS OF BUKHARA

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Abstract: This article provides information about the antiquity of Bukhara folk crafts, its distinctive features, delicacy and ornamentation, as well as the history of the creation of carpets, textile samples, sozanas, carving samples, and ceramics created in this area.

Key words: ancient traditions, arts, crafts, handicrafts, patterns, carpets, textiles, embroidery, pottery, ceramics.

BUXORO MILLIY HUNARMANDCHILIGI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Buxoro xalq hunarmandchiligining qadimiyligi u uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlaridan bo'lmish nozikligi va naqshinkorligi hamda bu makonda yaratilgan gilamlar, to'qimachilik namunalari, so'zanalar, o'ymakorlik namunalari, kulolchilik buyumlarining yaralish tarixi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qadimgi an'analar, san'at, hunarmandchilik, qo'l mehnati, naqsh, gilam, to'qimachilik, kashtachilik, so'zana, kulolchilik buyumlari.

НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ РЕМЕСЛА БУХАРЫ

Аннотация: В данной статье приведены сведения о древности бухарских народных промыслов, их отличительных чертах, изяществе и орнаментации, а также история создания ковров, образцов тканей, созан, образцов резьбы, керамики, созданных в этой местности.

Ключевые слова: древние традиции, искусство, ремесла, рукоделие, узоры, ковры, ткани, вышивка, гончарное дело, керамика.

INTRODUCTION

Bukhara is one of Uzbekistan's ancient cities. The ancient traditions of its world famous handicraft articles have evolved for centuries. Folklore, music, dancing, and other cultural traditions reflect the common people's emotion and spirituality. Creative skills, boundless thought, and understanding of poetry are reflected in the art of Bukhara.

Bukhara folk handicrafts employ various forms, materials and designs. Famous masters created unique designs with a harmony of colors and graphics. The artifacts, based on the shape of practical items, are characterized with symmetry and proportions of an object meant to be viewed from both long and short distances. The motifs are conventional and the colors are clear. Each motif has been named after a real object. These names have been originated from the original images or impressions of an object.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

One of the oldest kind of handicrafts spread amongst the people is textile. As Bukharan historian Narshahi writes, "The Bukhara textile enterprise 'Bait ut uroz' was famous all over the East for its products. Rulers of China and Rome wore clothes of their fabrics. The price of their silk clothes and one door curtain was equalled the annual tax revenue collected in Bukhara. "The production of silk fabric in the late centuries was also at a high level. These fabrics, in the 2nd half

of the 19th century, are characterized by small ornaments, lack of subjects, and lacking the development of lines and motifs. The colors consisted of soft and fine harmony of natural dyes: turquoise, blue, yellow and red rombs, cruciform vegetables and geometric patterns. Artisans began to apply artificial dyes to the fabrics with the name "abr", or cloud, and the general colour became richer and freer. The art of fabric painting was developed in Bukhara and the nearby villages Zandoni, Jondor, Romitan, and Vardonzi. On painted fabrics, ornaments of shub, flower, flower gardens and birds in the garden were the masters favourite motifs. At the beginning of the XX century, manufactured products ousted handicraft painted fabrics from the local bazaars and these kind of fabrics completely disappeared

The art of carpet weaving was practiced by Uzbek tribes, as well as Turkmen, Arab, and Kazaks, engaged in cattle breeding in Bukhara. Bukharan carpets stand out because of their technical parameters and especially because of their wood and pure dye. Bukharan carpets differ from other carpets because of the dyes made from plants, intricacy of designs and the harmony of warm colors. Today, a number of Bukharan carpet makers have been doing creative work to revive the secret of this art and to bring its fame up to applied art standards. Decorative needle work is the most popular national handicraft of Bukhara.

Needle work articles called "suzani", "sandalpush", "joipush" and others had decorative ornamentation of vegetable motifs and their colors were based on the proportions found between flowers and leaves. Somewhat tawdry and garish colors replaced the previous ones on articles. "Suzann's" were especially affected because the ornaments became larger as they became larger. Big sized articles were slightly untraditional and became symbol of family's wealth

RESEARCH RESULTS

The handicraft which reflects the experience and achievements accumulated by our ancestors and still created in Bukhara is gold embroidery. In The XIX and early XX century, this kind of art existed only in Bukhara. Gold embroidery is the art of sewing various ornaments and patterns on thick fabric with golden thread. There are two kinds of Bukharin gold embroidery. The "Zaminduzi" style is characterized by designs covering the whole surface of fabric. Geometric patterns ranging from simple straight and curved lines to complicated "Chireh" ornaments are applied in it. Men's clothes, their yaktag (robe worn in hot and warm weather) and robe were made from cotton fabric; richer people wore clothes made of "alocha"-half ik and makhsikovush - national shoes made of soft leather. Turbans worn by officials were decorated with gold and silver threads: skillfully lied round turban looked as wholly gold embroidered. The length, form, color and fabric of a turban showed a person's social positional. For example white turban was for the dergy, kybe - for Ali's descendants, blue for merchant, a turban in a minaret shape was for military people. Women's cloth was seen wholly and had a straight silhouette. Clothes of one color, looked very monolithic. The clothes' brims, collars, sleeves of these monolith dresses were embroidered with figured ornaments - jeyak-zekh. This custom originating from very ancient times is a result of people's belief that they protected their owner from evil, wicked spirits and almightiness. To decorate the interior of houses like in other countries was also traditional in Bukhara.

Paying the main attention to the decoration of the drawing (Puest) room was very typical, although the rooms where they lived themselves had a very modest decoration. Usually the walls, ceilings, doors and wicket-gates of a house were beautified with wonderful engraving and painting. Carpets, suranies, ceramics and engraved articles decorated his tent with carpets, strip of carpet, sack with figured ornament and also with long woven felt which firmly tied the tent beautifying

it. Both large and small panels are decorated with simplified flowers, irises and wide plains. At the beginning of the 20th century, the character of pictures began to resemble real images. Painters began to appreciate the natural state of objects and with their brushes they depicted willows, pomegranate trees, and bouquets of flowers.

DISCUSSION

Wood carving and painting have a very old history in Bukhara. The first usually decorated trunks made of hard wood, reading stands, wooden book covers, and trunks. The second type decorated small cupboards, "ubaiduy" doors, saddles and infant beds or cradles. Both methods show design motifs of the natural world, such as beautiful flowers, fruit trees, and detailed leaves. Carved doors are usually divided into three parts. The design carved on each part is different, and although each section looks separate from a short distance, the sections create one larger design when seen from a longer distance. The carving method used was multi perspective, thus relief mixed with bas-relief increased the complexity of the design and structure. Rings and domes made with metal were used to provide completeness to gates and doors. The great skill of Bukharan masters is brightly reflected in the carved wood, graceful arches, and majestic columns. The art of painting wood consisted of complex compositions that were completely carved into the surface of doors and articles and then partially painted over with green, red, blue, and gold paint. Basically they made the form of difficult plants, geometric and epigraphic designs on the surface of round basins. From the second half of the last century they began to make basins like oval quadrangular and other designs. The decorations of these basins were closely connected with the different designs of Arabic writing. Two sculptures of lions made of Garden marble which are placed in summer residence of Olimkhon is the result of great monumental art.

Bukhara jewelers especially used ruby and diamond from Badakhshan, turquoise from Iran, coral, pear, and mother of pearl from India... From early age girls wore ear-rings, rings and bracelets. On their cloths they put the paws of a bear and affixed art and were famous for he variety of form and category, we can see the things of jewelers art which decorated the head, forehead, ear, nose, neck, chest, back and hands.

CONCLUSION

Present days there are many young popular masters who took our education from Salimjon Hamidof who was popular in Bukhara in 1950. a great number of national masters worked in the field of metal chasing art of Bukhara both in kind and new meaning. The art of ceramics. As the second half of the 19th century the Art of Ceramics was developed in Gijduvan, Vobkent and Vazdanzy regions of Bukhara ceramic art centers.

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